

Digital India: A Futuristic Approach towards Education and Skilling

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Abstract:

Digital India represents the India that will connect Indians to different government facilities at a one click. These facilities include online government services that cover education and skilling, agriculture, digital infrastructure, emerging technologies, e-counseling, entrepreneurship and manufacturing, healthcare and wellness, social empowerment transport and logistics, state projects.

This research paper mainly focuses on education and skilling in Digital India. It covers different facilities provided by Government of India for example E- Counseling, CollabCAD, CollabGEO, Digital India Bhashini, Punarjjani, Visvesvaraya PhD Scheme, e-Granthalaya, Learning Management System, FutureSkills Prime, Mission Karmyogi, Academic Bank of Credits, National Academic Depositories.

Communication became a necessary thing for humans when they start living together in groups. Human communication changes its form from gestures, hand movements to the oral communication. It helps to transfer their thoughts from one person to other. Communication was present not only in the oral format but also in texts and pictures. Communication process changes with the time. People used a face-to-face communication in the past. They also made a use of birds for transferring a secret message from one place to other. As time passes different communication devices generated that can be used to contact a person present at a long distance.

Now a day's smart phones, internet, computer and social media made a human life easier than before. People adapted to this techno savvy world. They are using different social media platforms for a communication like Facebook, Whatsapp, Messenger, LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram, Youtube, Google forms, etc. Media plays an important role in communication. The world comes together with these

communication methods. Communication through such online media made a platform for Digital India.

Digital India represents the India that will connect Indians to different government facilities at a one click. These facilities include online government services that cover education and skilling, agriculture, digital infrastructure, emerging technologies, e-counseling, entrepreneurship and manufacturing, healthcare and wellness, social empowerment transport and logistics, state projects. Education and skilling facility explained in detail as given below.

Education and Skilling:

Education and skilling provide different facilities to students via different sections like E-Counseling, CollabCAD, CollabGEO, Digital India Bhashini, Punarjjani, Visvesvaraya PhD Scheme, e-Granthalaya, Learning Management System, FutureSkills Prime, Mission Karmyogi, Academic Bank of Credits, National Academic Depositories, DIKSHA.

1. **E-Counselling:** It is an online useful facility for students who want to take admission into different educational institutes present in India. It will provide a simple and transparent process from applying for specific course to take admission into different educational institutes and colleges. It will help students, counseling boards and institutes. This facility works on merit and reservation policies of Government of India.
2. **CollabCAD:** It is a computer program for the students of Engineering. It provides an online work of designing of 2D modelling transformation into a 3D product parts assembling. It will be a great tool for learners, Engineers, researchers to make changes in design as per their ideas.
3. **CollabGEO:** It is a 2D geometry tool for schoolteachers and students. It helps teachers to teach geometry to the students of class 6-9. It turns the teaching learning process into a fun game.
4. **Digital India Bhashini:** It works as a language translator for websites. It helps to connect a company to their customers present at different parts of multilingual India. It also celebrates the beauty of the local languages present in the India.
5. **Punarjjani:** It is online software specially designed for specially abled children. The algorithm of the software designed according to the need of learners. This transforms a manual procedure of teaching process into a digital one. It will encourage students to learn in online mode.
6. **Visvesvaraya PhD Scheme:** This scheme is to encourage students to take admission for PhD programmes across India. It provides fellowships for research students, PhD scholars and Post-doctoral fellows. It is a very good initiative by the Indian Government.
7. **E-Granthalaya:** This facility provides an online library services for teachers, students, researchers and learners. It had already started in 2002 with the version 1.0. The recent version of this digital platform will be 4.0. It had already been used by 7,000 libraries of India.
8. **Learning Management System:** As the name indicates, it is a software programme of learning developed for Government employees. It helps them to perform their duty with an ease in online mode. It will help Government employees in their work to administer, maintain their records and train others by providing e learning through courses.
9. **FutureSkills Prime:** It is a knowledge-based facility in future skills and a production of MeitY, National Association of Software and Service companies NASSCOM. It provides future skills to students in the form of courses, pathways, experiential learning that are necessary for their development in the field of artificial intelligence, data analytics, quantum computing, semiconductors, robotic process automation, virtual reality, web and mobile development, 3D printing, modeling, etc. Courses are available at discount. Experiential learning will provide industrial experience of hands-on training and practical to the learners. It will open the doors of job opportunities in industries for young talents of India.
10. **Mission Karmyogi:** It is a government national programme of online learning for civil servants to work efficiently and effectively for public. This platform was launched in 2022 to provide different online courses. Its main aim is to improve government-public relations for the betterment of society.
11. **Academic Bank of Credits:** It is an educational facility for students to transfer

their credits from one programme to other while studying in higher educational institute or college. It is helpful for undergraduate (degree), diploma and postgraduate diploma students. Student must have the unique ID (APAAR ID) for this purpose to take benefits of this facility. It is compulsory for college students as per National Education Policy 2020.

12. National Academic Depository: This initiative provides an online storage facility of documents like mark-sheets, award certificates for the students. It provides digital security to these documents. Student can access this facility anytime and anywhere.

13. DIKSHA: It is a knowledge-based platform for school students and teachers. The main function of this platform is to provide online school education for all. It consists of different programmes such as Nipun Bharat, Bhasha Sangam, e- Jaadui Pitara, Education For All, Virtual Lab, Vocational Education.

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